

Architectural and cultural heritage as a driver of social change in rural areas: 10 years (2009–2019) of management and recovery in Huete, a town of Cuenca, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Suitable management and recovery of architectural and cultural heritage contribute to promote the development of rural towns. This was the case of the work done for 10 years by the Fundación Huete Futuro (the Huete Future Foundation; FHF) in the town of Huete in Cuenca (Spain). This study intended to identify the drivers of impact and the social changes that this heritage management led to. To do so, two methodological approaches were employed: Participatory Impact Pathway Analysis (PIPA) and Positive Social Change (PSC). The main obtained results corresponded to the physical restoration of buildings of historic interest for Huete and the promotion of activities of cultural interest. Moreover, the integration of and social participation in the planning and management process for recovering heritage were also promoted. This heritage management and its revaluation promoted tourist activities that favoured rural development and encouraged a change in social behaviour. The population began to perceive its heritage as a means towards empowerment and innovation.

1. Introduction

Architectural and cultural heritage in rural communities is an asset of collective interests (López et al., 2012) made up of inherited tangible and intangible attributes. These attributes can benefit the community's present and future societies (Dela and Anril, 2019) Amit-Cohen and Sofer (2016) and allow the past to be commemorated while the community becomes a tourist attraction and a source of entertainment and commercial use. Heritage is identified as a living leverage to fight against imposed structural limitations. Such a heritage is ever-changing. It is built from selected elements that are considered typical of a culture and it is essential that a society is identified by (Medina, 2017). Cultural and architectural heritage gives meaning and direction to local territories when it is considered as something invaluable that is owned by the local people. This consideration and ownership brings about a source of opportunities to promote positive attitudes, drive collective potential and reinforce the town's capacities (Carpio, 2000). It also creates learning opportunities through the study of three main aspects: the role of its settlements; the location of its settlements; and the integration of its settlements towards rural development. In this way, heritage elements are incarnated in values and the present vision of the past, and

their activation depends on political powers. This activation is often previously facilitated by society when the population highlights these values as a result of identitarian processes (Prats, 2005).

The importance that rural heritage gains depends on how its attributes are being represented and used. This use of heritage is conditioned by the local capacity and institutional support to manage it (Caravaca et al., 1996). Good management facilitates its being valued and conserved, and may have mid and long-term socio-cultural and economic impacts (Martín and Martín, 2016). Along these lines, the European Union has acknowledged and promoted conserving heritage as a means to manifest the local cultural value (Kratzer and Ammering, 2019). Such conservation requires sustainable planning and management strategies. Public participation plays a key role in this (Fatorić and Seekamp, 2017).

The management of rural heritage through territorial planning and land use policies facilitate the integrated understanding and valuation of its natural, architectural, and cultural components. Inclusion of the territorial dimension and land use in the concept of heritage is key to its understanding, treatment, and management. The protection of assets is as important as the appreciation of urban environments and different land uses. The rural geographic space understood as part of the heritage

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is known as "Territorial Heritage". In the regional town and country planning of Spain (Junta de Andalucía. Consejería de Vivienda y Ordenación del Territorio, 2006) the territory is conceived as a mosaic of protected spaces and physically and functionally articulated elements. This system implements planning policies and instruments as a framework to protect, disseminate, and enhance how territorial cultures emerge. Territorial Heritage is thus defined as a geographical space constructed by humans from an original physical substratum. Low of Spanish Historical Heritage, intending to address heritage protection from a territorial approach, defines a "Heritage Area" as diverse and complementary assets that represent human evolution with value for the use and enjoyment of the community (Florido Trujillo, G, 2013).

Suitable heritage management allows the acceleration of rural development, production, and access to new products, processes and services. The main objective of heritage management must be to improve people's quality of life and social interaction, which is fundamental for the planning process (Provenzano et al., 2016). This management acts as a means to: (1) extend state action by joint decision making with local communities; (2) ensure the fair exchange of tasks to generate empowerment in marginal groups; (3) facilitate the constant development and joint strengthening of institutions (Cundill et al., 2013); (4) mitigate juvenile emigration, create jobs and retain human capital from rural areas (Martín and Martín, 2016); and (5) facilitate resilience in response to rural decline (Li et al., 2019).

Jimura (2011) points out the importance of well managed heritage as part of the economic, cultural and social change process in rural areas. On the one hand, it encourages not only the mobilisation of existing resources, but also new projects in these lands (Troitiño, 1998). It promotes places of interest being physically restored and facilitates town planning to protect and disseminate them (Rodríguez, 1998). On the other hand, it encourages looking for stakeholders and building social interaction networks (Markey et al., 2008). These networks promote aid in some situations of limited resources, generate processes to exchange knowledge and experiences; and collect useful information and provide social empowerment opportunities (Moulin and Boniface, 2010). The ideas that originate from these networks create a vision of development and tend to materialise as projects with which they are identified and committed (Parrado et al., 2009).

The objective of this research is to analyse the heritage management mechanisms employed by the Fundación Huete Futuro (the Huete Future Foundation; FHF) in the Huete town of Cuenca (Spain) and its results concerning the recovery of the architectural, cultural and social heritage of its community. To do so, the intention was to answer the following research questions: (1) which factors made it hard and/or easy for management to recover heritage?; (2) what were the main drivers of impact by which the heritage management results were diffused?; and (3) what main social changes have been made by highlighting heritage?

The second section of this article presents a literature review about the use and application of participative approaches in rural heritage management and conservation processes. The third section describes the chosen case study. The fourth section presents the methodology and developed tools. The fifth section offers the results and an analysis of the drivers of impact and the social change created through recovering heritage. The sixth section provides the conclusions drawn from the answers to the three research questions.

2. The participative approach in heritage management

Applying participative approaches to heritage management and conservation helps to integrate the knowledge, perspectives and priorities obtained from local areas (Ericson, 2006), and to exchange knowledge among multidisciplinary stakeholders (Li et al., 2020). Participation generates mechanisms to promote resilience and social commitment; to understand the context (Bustillos Ardaya et al., 2019); and to develop innovation, empowerment and social learning processes (Toderi et al., 2017). These mechanisms depend on three important

measures: participants; their interaction for decision making; and the link between discussions and public/political action (Fung, 2006).

Participative approaches allow the institutional practices and mechanisms to be identified that bring about positive changes in behaviour in society. Such social changes or impacts depend on each project's context and on participative co-creation. To understand these co-creation and innovation processes in participative mechanisms, certain tools exist like the Spiral of Innovation (Koutsouris and Zarakosta, 2019). This tool helps to understand different stages of innovation processes, performed activities and the involved stakeholders, whose cooperation depends on social identity, group cohesion and social distance (Baynes et al., 2016). In turn, the social impact generated by this cooperation can be affected by economic, cultural and social differences in rural communities. To detect these differences, participative approaches employ tools like semi-structured interviews, logical models, focus work groups and literature reviews (Eker et al., 2017).

Participative approaches facilitate conflict solving (Pérez et al., 2002) by communication processes based on diffusing information and integrating society into decision making. This integration helps participation strategies to spread and to generate common values (Kovács et al., 2016), which are key for encouraging collaborative governance, public deliberation and interactions among civil social groups (Gera, 2016; Erfani and Roe, 2019). The result is improved quality of decisions. Management processes are conferred legitimacy and interested parties' capacities are reinforced (Dietz, 2013). Participative approaches also promote shared authority practices through decentralised decision making, in part, because vertical government links exist. The local community is provided with power to manage its local heritage through suitable communication channels with the corresponding administrative organisations (Stenseke, 2009; Li et al., 2020).

Applying participative approaches in the present research enabled describe and recognize the management mechanisms set up by FHF that facilitated the community's architectural-cultural heritage recovering. Two participative approaches were followed: Participatory Impact Pathway Analysis (PIPA) and Positive Social Change (PSC). These approaches allowed information to be collected that answered the previously posed research questions. PIPA (Douthwaite et al., 2008) was used to understand impacts on agricultural and rural development projects (Douthwaite et al., 2007). PSC was employed to analyse the social impact generated by organisations that interact with their societies (Stephan et al., 2016).

PIPA, through participative interviews and workshops, allowed a logic model to be created with the results (Knowlton and Phillips, 2012) and to graphically analyse the performed management, the drivers of impact and the obtained results (Mayne, 2004). Social interaction networks were also identified (Alvarez et al., 2010). These are networks that favoured the results and that were formed by key stakeholders and institutions who managed the heritage recovery (Richards and Panfil, 2010). Applying PSC through interviews inspired in the Spiral of Innovation allowed the social impact generated by the recovery of Huete's architectural and cultural heritage to be analysed. The activities that stimulated a change in people's behaviour were identified at the PSC's three levels: Motivation, Capacity and Opportunity. The "Motivation" level corresponds to the organisational practices that develop people's intrinsic motivations. The "Capacity" level relates to those practices that stimulate development and putting local knowledge to good use. The "Opportunity" level identifies the organisational practices that allow inclusive governance structures, collaboration networks and innovation mechanisms to be created.

3. Case study

3.1. The Huete town context

The Huete town is located to the northwest of the province of Cuenca in the Spanish Autonomous Community called Castilla-La Mancha

Fig. 1. Where Huete is located.

(Fig. 1). Its population is made up of 1748 inhabitants (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2020). That population has declined (18% in the last 19 years) and aged (27% are aged over 65 years). It also receives some 700–800 people in the summer. Of its whole population, 60.82% work in the services sector; 21.65% work in agriculture; 10.31% work in industry; and 7.22% work in the building sector. The town’s centre houses many historical-artistic monuments that are being renovated or are at risk of deterioration (Servicio Público de Empleo Estatal SEPE, 2018).

3.2. The Huete Future Foundation

Huete is one of the towns with considerable architectural-cultural heritage in the province of Cuenca. Due to lack of care and conservation, its heritage has been completely abandoned for 50 years. This led the Hispania Nostra Association, a national association that shows interest in Spanish Cultural Heritage that is at risk of disappearing or of its values being altered. Two of Huete’s heritage assets are on its “Red List” (Lista Roja del Patrimonio, 2020). Apart from this, certain social and administrative problems have come into play, such as pessimism, passiveness, apathy and scarce to no management performed by local administrations (Fundación Huete Futuro, 2009).

The Huete Future Foundation (FHF) came into being in 2008 to help build a future for Huete and its administrative division. This is a private not-for-profit organisation that aims to rescue, restore, conserve and

promote the historical, archaeological, ethnographical and natural heritage of Huete. Its other objectives include: setting up channels to recover and highlight Huete’s heritage; revaluating the human resources that have left the town, but maintaining an emotional link; considering collaboration mechanisms with the local administration in relation to its heritage; and stressing the role of Huete’s architectural-cultural heritage in terms of economic, social and cultural revitalisation.

The FHF Trust is divided into three colleges (Fig. 2.). The first (maximum of 6 people) is formed by the Town Council through the mayor/mayorress and two councillors from the two most voted political parties. The second college is formed by a maximum of five representatives of associations from Huete (legal persons) and two representatives (natural persons) appointed by FHF members. The third college is represented by local people from Huete who wish to work to meet the Foundation’s purposes (minimum of six people). The maximum number of FHF members allowed to make up the Trust is 25. Moreover, the Foundation has created the Foundation’s Friends Network (FFN) that is made up of natural and legal persons. This network includes 375 people. Most of which live away, but are linked with the network as they were born in Huete. The FFN has no other responsibility that contribute economically, regularly and sporadically to facilitate performing activities that favour the town’s heritage. It also provides logistic support to required activities and helps to diffuse the obtained results to allow more people to join the network (Fundación Huete Futuro, 2009).

The FHF draws up an action plan every year which is the institutional

Fig. 2. Internal Mechanism of the Huete Futuro Foundation.

document that plans which actions and activities are to be carried out. From 2008–2019, 110 activities have been performed to work towards recovering heritage through three types of action: a) activities that make the FHF visible in local, provincial and regional areas, to facilitate management and contacts, and to encourage being rooted in Huete (40% of its activities); b) information activities that address the population, Foundations' Friends, collaborative organisations and the public administration (34% of activities); c) intervention activities to restore and recover Huete's architectural-cultural heritage. The third lot of activities represents 26% of the actions and requires bigger budgets and management of more time and efforts (Fundación Huete Futuro, 2009).

The FHF plays a triple role while performing these activities: a) a promoting stakeholder of intervention projects in heritage; b) a revitalising stakeholder, along with other association groups in the area, which motivates and raises the population's awareness about the socio-economic importance of recovering and managing heritage; and c) a stakeholder that collaborates with public-private organisations with heritage competences. The FHF works in cooperation with the Huete Town Council, the owner of most of the town's heritage. Collaboration results in performing works and technical studies, preliminary plans, etc., which guide and help to suitably channel technical and economic resources from public administrations and private organisations (Fundación Huete Futuro, 2009). The activities and projects undertaken by the FHF are shown in detail in Table 1 (see also Figs. 3–7) Fig. 8.

3.3. Huete's architectural and cultural heritage

The Huete town has a rich and varied architectural, civil, religious and cultural heritage. Huete was and is one of the most important monumental centres in the province of Cuenca. Of its historic-artistic architectural heritage, the following stand out: the town wall of 9th century Andalusí origin whose remains correspond to the most primitively built adobe walls; the Luna Castle or Wabda Citadel of Andalusí origin, at the top of which Neolithic tools have been found; and convents and monasteries, of which eight still exist and only three still stand: the Jesuits Convent-School, our Lady of Mercy Monastery, the Jesus and Mary Monastery of Justinian nuns. There were also 10 parish churches, of which the remains of only three are conserved: Santa María de Atienza Church, the oldest of them all, and the St. Peter's and Trinity Churches. The civil architecture remains include the Clock Tower, the Royal Granary, and the nobles' Houses-Palace built between the 15th and 18th centuries. Nowadays, Huete exhibits its heritage remains in five museums. The Floreació de la Fuente Museum houses an interesting international contemporary art collection, while the Antonio Pérez Foundation Photography Museum has a room for temporary exhibitions. The Religious Art Museum includes gold- and silverware made for worship from the 16th to 19th centuries, as well as a collection of ornaments and liturgical vestments from the 16th to 18th centuries. The

Ethnographic Museum has a collection of traditional craftwork tools from the Natural Alcarria area of Cuenca. The (private) Forge Museum exhibits a collection of tools and wrought iron works. Finally, an interpretation centre exists in relation to the Atienza district festivals as does a traditional cave/wine cellar that has been converted into a museum (González, 2016).

4. Methodology

This research began by analysing the documents issued by FHF. Then the PIPA approach was applied by means of a participative workshop and a semi-structured interview. A logic model was built from the results. Next the PSC application was followed, which allowed analysis of the social change brought about through the mechanisms and practices that the Foundation promoted.

4.1. Analysing documents

Before field data collection took place, a preliminary analysis was carried out of all the activities performed by FHF between 2008 and 2019. This information is documented in the 25 reports that the Foundation has edited. They contain technical studies of infrastructures of heritage interest, budget analyses, cultural events, informative meetings and finished administrative proceedings. They also helped to identify the participating key stakeholders and organisations in such activities, determining factors and administrative or economic difficulties. This preliminary analysis indicated which material needed to be prepared for the participative workshop and determined how the interview would be designed. These activities are explained below.

4.2. Participatory Impact Pathway Analysis (PIPA)

Application of PIPA began with a participative 2-hour workshop held in the Huete Town Hall with five representatives of the FHF Trust. Each participant received the problems tree, which was previously prepared according to the information acquired from the initial analysis of all the documents. The participants ratified the causes, problems and effects identified in 2008 which led to the establishment of the Foundation. Then the participants were handed a timeline, which was also prepared beforehand. It identified all the activities, projects, cultural events, competitions and festivals promoted by FHF and the key stakeholders involved in them. The results were collected using the problems tree, and the timeline identified the key factors of the process and the stakeholders that would be interviewed.

The interviews held with the stakeholders collaborated with the Foundation helped to identify the perspectives of both the stakeholders and the local population in relation to heritage and the importance of its management. The Foundation's management was considered

Table 1
Activities and projects undertaken by the Huete Future Foundation (2009–2019).

Promoting the restoration of architectural heritage	Revitalising activities of heritage interest	Collaborating with other organisations to recover heritage
Restoring nine canvases altruistically by the FFN: 2009–2018	Campaign "Decorate your home, brighten up your town" XI Ediciones: 2008–2019	Collaborating in restoring the Jesus and Mary Convent to house a photograph museum: 2011 Budget: €618,479.26
Ideas competition to restore the St Santa Maria de Atienza Church: 2009	Editing 25 " Huete Future Foundation" reports: 2009–2019	Restoring the paintings "St. Joseph with the Boy" and "St. John the Baptist": 2012
Drawing up a preliminary plan to regenerate the old Jesuits school: 2010.	Informative meetings XI Ediciones: 2009–2019	Collaborating to restore the Santa Maria de Atienza Church apse: 2013. Budget: €360,000
Condition the small square in the Valdemoro del Rey District: 2011	Website and social networks: 2009–2019	Coordinating the work group to write new subsidiary aesthetic regulations of Huete constructions and the final writing of the document proposed to be included in Urban planning: 2017
Restoring the del Moro Passage: 2013	Series of summer solstice jazz concerts IX Ediciones: 2009–2019	Collaborating in the regeneration of the Jesuit School/Convent to be used as a hotel: 2018–2020 Budget: €2700,000
Remodelling the Religious Art Museum: 2013	Series of Christmas concerts VII Ediciones: 2009–2015	
Recreating an audiovisual of the "The Candle Legend" in Santa Maria de Atienza Church crypt: 2014.	Awareness campaign about the Huete cucumber XI Ediciones: 2009–2019	
Tourist signposting about Huete's heritage: 2014	Classic cars exhibition and the Alcarria Rally Conquense in 2012	
Buying rustic land around the town walls and other physical structures of heritage interest: 2014–2018	"Buy in Huete" Campaign VII Ediciones: 2013–2019	
Restoring a traditional wine cellar cave of Cerro de Santa Ana: 2017	1 "Challenges and Opportunities of Spanish Historical Heritage in Rural Areas" Symposium: 2017	
Gastronomic Gourmet Fairs: 2017–2018	Innovative ideas competition: 2018	
Writing up a Master Plan for the Huete Walls in the north and the end of the eastern side: 2018		
Buying the land site adjacent to the Jesuits school: 2018		
Archaeological study of the "El Borbotón" architectural saltwater aqueduct: 2019		

Table 1 (continued)

Geophysical exploration study with a 3D ground-penetrating radar on the Alvar-Fáñez hill and the north wall: 2019

innovative, which was why the interview was designed following the Spiral of Innovation (Koutsouris and Zarokosta, 2019). This design identified four stages as part of innovation processes in heritage management, and each inspired several questions. Stage 1 corresponded to the sources of inspiration and motivation to set up the Foundation and its activities, and four questions were used. Stage 2 involved the identification of the factors, stakeholders and organisations that made the management process easy or hard. Seven questions were used. Stage 3 corresponded to the mechanisms of disseminating and consolidating the necessary management activities to recover heritage, for which five questions were used. Stage 4 corresponded to the analysis of the social change in the population, which came about through recovering heritage. Six questions were used and led to a 22-question survey (see Appendix A).

Those participating in the interviews sought to cover all the interested parties: a) the people who took part in the process to set up the Foundation; b) the representatives of the Huete associations; c) friends and members of the Foundation; d) representatives of the involved public administrations; and e) local people from Huete. These interviews were characterised by gender, age group, education and the type of relationship held with the Foundation (see Table 2). The predominating age group was 30–50 years (more than 50%) and the level of education was dominated by the third level (more than 60%). Interviews were held individually and lasted 30–45 min. They were transcribed, and descriptive codes, followed by more interpretative theme codes, were used (Erfani and Roe, 2019).

A logic model was built with the results of the participative workshop and interviews (Knowlton and Phillips, 2012). This is explained and developed in the Results section. It allowed graphical identification of the recourses required and the activities performed by the FHF, which later generated certain products, outcomes and impacts.

4.3. Positive social change (PSC)

This approach allowed an analysis of the practices promoted by the Foundation that brought about a positive social change. By means of the aforementioned interviews, these practices were identified and classified according to the three PSC levels: Motivation, Capacity and Opportunity (Stephan et al., 2016). Those that promoted intrinsic motivations were at the "Motivation" level; those that have stimulated a change in behaviour by people's own free will. The practices that stimulated knowledge building through the local population's own capacity and got all the interested parties involved were positioned at the "Capacity" level. These practices allowed the processes that generated connective leadership to be identified. Finally, at the "Opportunity" level came the practices that promoted social inclusion and the creation of interaction networks which, in turn, motivated society's empowerment. This level included the sustainable projects supported by innovation, which allowed human and economic resources to be mobilised.

5. Results

The results presented in this section are arranged in three subsections. Subsection 5.1 analyses the four factors that influenced the recovery of the heritage identified by the local population. Subsection 5.2 analyses the main drivers of impact; the horizontal/vertical diffusion of the results; and the social interaction networks by the logic model of

Fig. 3. The Santa Maria de Atienza Church apse before (2009) and after its restoration (2015).

Fig. 4. Wine cellar on the St Ana hill before (2016) and after restoration (2019).

Fig. 5. Religious Art Museum before (2009) and after restoration (2014).

Fig. 6. The Moro passage before (2009) and after restoration (2013).

Fig. 7. First symposium “Challenges and Opportunities of Spanish Historical Heritage in Rural Areas” (2016).

Fig. 8. The Huete Gastronomic Gourmet Fair held in the Jesus and Mary Convent in October 2017.

Table 2
Profile of interviewees.

	Live in Huete	Do not live in Huete
Gender		
Female	3 (12%)	4 (16%) 9 (36%)
Male	9 (36%)	13 (52%)
Total	12 (48%)	
Age group	4 (16%)	7 (28%)
30–50 years	3 (12%)	5 (20%)
51–70 years	5 (20%)	1 (4%)
71 and older	12 (48%)	13(52%)
Total		
Education	-	-
Primary	5 (20%)	0 (0%)
Secondary	9 (36%)	11(44%)
University	14 (56%)	11(44%)
Total		
Type of stakeholder	4 (16%)	6 (24%)
Foundation’s Friends	4 (16%)	3 (12%)
Foundation Members	4 (16%)	1 (4%)
Belonging to other associations	-	3 (12%)
Civil servants and politicians	12 (48%)	13 (52%)
Total		

the results in Fig. 9. Finally, subsection 5.3 analyses the institutional practices and mechanisms that brought about a change in social behaviour.

5.1. Factors affecting heritage management

The analysis of the interviews identified the first factor, namely the capacity to mobilise economic resources. These resources were mobilised through public-private subsidising, along with the voluntary economic payments made sporadically by the Foundation’s Friends. This

mobilisation of economic resources helped to plan, undertake and collaborate with the projects and activities listed in Table 1. Moreover, the fact that the Foundation lacked its own funds and its management depended on subsidies being approved and on voluntary payments limited other projects from being immediately undertaken. Examples of such projects are the geophysical exploration project by 3D ground-penetrating radar on the Alvar-Fáñez hill and the surroundings of the town wall, or the archaeological study of the El Borbotón saltwater aqueduct. These projects are awaiting the requested subsidies. Notwithstanding, the Foundation as a promoter facilitated the ideas, technical documents and master plans.

The second factor corresponds to FHF Trust members’ personal capacities, thanks to their different competences, attitudes and qualities that have enabled activities and projects to recover heritage to be managed and carried out. The population’s appreciation of their level of knowledge, tenacity and vision has motivated more citizens to participate. One clear example of such is the 375 people who are participating as Foundation’s Friends. Personal capacities have led to the establishment of economic, technical, research and social collaboration networks. The results have been disseminated locally. According to the interviews, the generational renewal of trust members could involve a risk factor for the Foundation’s sustainability. They consider that people entering the Foundation with the same capacities and social commitments, who are willing to invest time in the Foundation and in Huete’s future, could be a “complicated” matter.

The third factor corresponds to the emotional value, a feeling of belonging and the commitment that Huete symbolises for representatives, friends and the population in general. This factor was fundamental for FHF’s creation and also for its sustainability through permanent management activities. “Love for the town”, “personal satisfaction”, and “unselfish” and “altruistic” work are values that emerge from raising

Fig. 9. The logic model of the results from the PIPA methodological framework.

awareness and the historic value of Huete. “Every idea is important, no matter how small it is” explained one of the interviewees who considered that all ideas help to improve the abandoned heritage situation.

The fourth factor appears with the Huete heritage potential and wealth, as reflected in documents and technical studies like: *News about the Foundation, antiquity and history of the Huete Town*, written by J.A. Alique in 1768; *Historic curiosities of the Huete Town*, written by Amor Calzas in 1904; *Huete from prehistory to the middle ages*, by I. López Gonzáles in 1995; *The urban structure of Huete in the 15th century*, written by J.M Benito in 1994; *Huete and new contributions from humanities*, directed by González Abad Luisa in 2016; and a doctoral thesis, *Baroque architecture in Huete and its land*, written by José Luis García Martínez in 2015. According to the interviews, the architectural recovery projects that have more strongly impacted the population were the Religious Art Museum, recovering the Ape and the Santa María de Atienza Church Crypt and the Moro Passage. Moreover, the social impact of cultural activities, such as the gastronomic fairs and the awareness campaign about growing and eating the Huete Cucumber, led to two new organisations being set up: the Horticulture Association and the Huete Land Gourmet Association, which promote quality gastronomic products. Other cultural and educational activities are also promoted by the Foundation, such as concerts, awareness campaigns like “Decorate your home, brighten up your town”, and the 1st “Challenges and Opportunities of Spanish Historical Heritage in Rural Areas” Symposium. These have been identified by the population as fundamental means for the town’s rural development.

5.2. Drivers of impact from heritage management

The logic model built with the results (Knowlton and Phillips, 2012) and shown in Fig. 9, describes, from left to right, the required resources, the planned specific activities, the generated products, the horizontal/vertical diffusion of the results (Córdoba and White, 2011) and the produced social impact. Point 5.2.1 describes the drivers of impact, which correspond to the process of obtaining the first required products and the subsequent social impact. Point 5.2.2 offers the results of the short-, mid- and long-term horizontal/vertical diffusion activities.

Finally, point 5.2.3 describes the consolidated networks of social interaction.

5.2.1. Description of the drivers of impact

The description of the drivers of impact initially includes resources, the means needed to plan the Foundation’s activities. They are human and financial means; a deteriorating heritage; the Huete Town Council’s institutional support; strategic resources and knowledge about how public administrations operate; and a sense of belonging and commitment with the town. The scope of these resources and their knowledge facilitated the planning of three activities (the second column in Fig. 9) which represent three pillars of the Foundation’s activities: visibility activities performed locally, provincially and regionally; information activities that address the population, the administration, organisations and the Foundation’s Friends; and intervention activities to restore and recover architectural-cultural heritage. The first products were obtained by correctly planning these activities (third column in Fig. 9): the local, provincial and regional administrations intervening and participating to recover Huete’s heritage; economic resources; revaluating heritage elements; informative meetings and diffusing the Foundation’s work through reports; preparing technical documents and drawing up master plans; and buying land and physical structures of heritage interest.

Apart from these three pillars of action, the Foundation also plays a triple role: as a promoter; a revitalising agent; and a collaborative agent with public-private organisations that have heritage competences. These mechanisms of action have helped the local, provincial and regional administrations intervene and participate in recovering architectural-cultural heritage. These administrations have facilitated the necessary economic means so that many of the works devised and studied by the Foundation would materialise. We need to consider that recovering architecture heritage involves a short-, mid- and long-term process, depending on whether economic resources are available.

Cultural recovery is a simple process that has been carried out since the first year that the Foundation came into being. FHF has performed different activities to encourage interaction and social participation. For the present research work, the cultural and training activities promoted by FHF during the 2008–2019 period were analysed. According to the

interviewees, the stronger social impact were: cultural activities, like the jazz concerts offered in Santa Maria de Atienza Apse; the gastronomic fairs; the awareness campaigns about producing and eating local products like the Huete cucumber; and the 1st “Challenges and Opportunities of Spanish Historical Heritage in Rural Areas” Symposium. All these activities have promoted the revaluation of heritage elements and the recovery of cultural traditions from the area.

Every year the Foundation organises informative meetings as part of the information activities that it performs to address the population and the Friends network. These meetings are intended to encourage the local population to participate. The population is also given informative material, like the reports prepared by FHF, to diffuse the results obtained by the heritage recovery process. Such diffusion aims to also engage the population in the planning process; motivate people to participate voluntarily; and strengthen the economic and research collaboration networks.

As part of the intervention activities in relation to architectural heritage, FHF has drawn up different master plans and technical documents. Some examples are: the preliminary plan for the Jesuits Convent regeneration work (2011); the Huete wall master plan (2018); and the geophysical exploration study with 3D ground-penetrating radar on the Alvar-Fáñez hill and the northern wall side (2019). Presently, it is preparing an archaeological study about the “El Borbotón” saltwater aqueduct (2019). It has also intervened in coordinating the writing of new aesthetic regulations that the building/restoration projects must comply with, and has bought land and physical structures of heritage interest, which currently form part of most of the recovered material assets. Its work maintains synergy with the local administration and encourages cooperation and values that focus on the town’s socio-economic development.

The activities and projects undertaken by the Foundation have facilitated the understanding, management, and valuation of the local architectural and cultural heritage from a holistic and integrating perspective. This perspective is consistent with the land use and territorial planning of the Spanish regions (Junta de Andalucía. *Consejería de Vivienda y Ordenación del Territorio, 2006*) as it fosters the internal cohesion of rural areas. Heritage interventions have brought changes in land use policy in those areas related to architectural elements such as: a) the restoration of the Santa Maria de Atienza apse, where a degraded space was recovered to transform it into a new scenic space; b) the acquisition of rustic land in the surroundings of the town Wall to convert it into spaces for its protection, incorporating recreative areas; c) restoration of a traditional wine cave, a deteriorated and worthless space transformed into a revalued tourist destination converting it into an example for similar spaces in the locality; d) the purchase of the land adjacent to the Jesuit school, whose initial use was linked to the construction of private housing and it is currently being used as a tourist infrastructure and will form part of the Castilla-La Mancha Hotel Network; e) Restoring the del Moro Passage, an urban space located in the centre of the city, deteriorated in the past by private actions and it has been converted into a tourist and recreational attraction for the town.

These tangible results have stemmed from identifying needs that favour the recovery of Huete’s architectural-cultural heritage and also promote a change in social behaviour. Details are provided below.

5.2.2. The vertical and horizontal diffusion of the results

Vertical diffusion is understood as institutional mechanisms, namely regulations, policies and models which, by means of Huete’s architectural-cultural recovery, encourage the results being diffused to and adopted by the local population. Diffusing these results to the local population is known as horizontal diffusion (Córdoba and White, 2011). Both the horizontal and vertical diffusions of results are reflected in the logic model in Fig. 9, where they appear as short-, mid- and long-term results. These results were mainly dependant on economic factors and the Foundation’s management capacity. Its distribution in time was

done through the preliminary analysis of the FHF reports and the PIPA analysis.

As seen in Fig. 9, the short-term results (1–3 years), thanks to the Foundations’ management (vertical diffusion), include: introducing heritage as a socio-economic resource into the political agenda; raising awareness about the value of local production as a means to generate economic resources; recovering architectural-cultural heritage; identifying volunteers and public-private institutions to provide economic, research and social support (detailed later as social interaction networks); diffusing the Foundation on social networks; the social, institutional and administrative interaction; and increasing the Friends network. These short-term results have favoured the diffusion of results to the population and it adopting them (horizontal diffusion). Finally, the mid- and long-term results have been promoted.

In relation to the obtained mid- and long-term results, the recovery of Huete’s architectural-cultural heritage continues to progress considerably. This is because the Foundation has developed participative management processes (vertical diffusion) and promoted the population’s participation by means of innovative ideas and competitions (horizontal diffusion) that form part of heritage recovery. By such processes, the local population has contributed ideas to revalue heritage as a way towards socio-economic development, and to encourage knowledge exchange and social learning. These competitions have led to 14 ideas, led by these three ideas: “Huete: the Bookshop Town”, “The Frescoes Route” and “Hospitable Huete”. These ideas have been included in the Foundation’s yearly planning to seek the required means and, when they become available, to materialise them by adequate management.

The Huete Town Council, in collaboration with the socio-economic recovery work that the Foundation carries out, promoted the privatisation of the tourist office (vertical diffusion). This enabled new mechanisms to be set up to encourage cultural tourism in the town’s inland areas (horizontal diffusion). To diffuse architectural-cultural heritage wealth, the tourist office is planning new heritage activities to generate economic resources in the town. So the tourist office is promoting ways of life in rural areas to include: farms, shepherds, farmers, cheese factories, honey, kitchen gardens and a tapas tour with cucumber as the main ingredient. Routes are organised around the old town quarter during which the work done to recover the main churches, monuments, convents, museums and buildings of historic interest is stressed and made visible. This has tripled tourism in the area in the past 10 years and has encouraged owners of businesses to innovate and offer new products to tourists. It is worth stressing FHF’s management and collaboration roles, which have allowed regional economic support to be obtained for the regeneration work done on the Jesuits School, which will be used as a hotel to encourage tourism.

All this demonstrates that public-private institutional support and the Foundation’s management have been essential for the town’s rural development. The analysis of the effects produced through rural tourism showed that the population’s capacities had clearly been strengthened. Mechanisms of entrepreneurship and support to promote local production were identified which, in turn, produced economic resources. An example of such is the promotion and sale of artisanal products, such as lavanda liqueurs and honey-based products. Another example would be increased local cucumber production as a result of awareness campaigns about the “Huete Cucumber”, which has also been promoted by FHF since 2009. These campaigns draw the attention of the business people who produce gin and employ the “Huete Cucumber” as one of its ingredients. Children’s cooking workshops are also run that feature cucumber as the main ingredient (horizontal diffusion).

Sources of finance have had to be found to materialise architectural recovery projects. Through its management, the Foundation has managed to identify and set up economic support networks formed by public-private institutions (vertical diffusion). It is important to highlight that both architectural projects and cultural activities have been devised from within the Foundation, but these institutions’ economic support has facilitated them being materialised. The joint collaboration

between these institutions and the Foundation has led to heritage recovery outcomes, and has also encouraged the diffusion and adoption of these outcomes locally. This local acceptance (horizontal diffusion) is reflected in the larger number of Foundation's Friends (currently standing at 375). It is also reflected by young people engaging in FHF's activities.

In short, the horizontal and vertical diffusion of results have been mechanisms promoted by the triple role that the Foundation plays, thanks to public-private institutional support. These diffusion mechanisms have helped the Foundation to become deeply rooted in the town. Accordingly, the Foundation's innovative management is considered a management model that can be used by other towns with heritage wealth. Finally, the logical model shown in Fig. 9 shows the impact identified by all the results in time and through institutional mechanisms. Here the impact comes over as a positive social change of both society and public institutions when faced with valuing and acknowledging Huete's architectural-cultural heritage as a socio-economic potential.

5.2.3. Consolidating interaction networks

The building and consolidation of interaction networks are the result of seeking public-private institutions as financial, technical, research and administrative means of support. These networks have helped the heritage recovery activities/projects to materialise and have been identified by holding interviews and organising the participative workshop.

The economic aid network is made up of the Huete Town Council (public); the Provincial Council Offices of Cuenca (public); the CEDER Natural Alcarria of Cuenca (public/private); the Regional Government of the Castilla-la Mancha Autonomous Community (public); the Antonio Pérez Foundation (private); IBM España (private); LiberBank (private); the Globalcaja Saving Bank (private); and Foundation's Friends (currently 375 friends). The population understands that economic support is one of the most limiting factors for performing new heritage recovery works. Indeed, those interviewed stressed the importance of seeking a way towards self-management for each project and planned activity instead of depending on subsidies.

The research support network made up of the International Menéndez y Pelayo University which, along with the Foundation and Huete Town Council, organised the 1st "Challenges and Opportunities of Spanish Historical Heritage in Rural Areas" Symposium held in 2016 for the general population. This symposium reflected on the importance of safeguarding the architectural-cultural heritage of Spanish rural communities and allowed a relationship to be established with not only professionals in rural development and in heritage recovery and management, but also with representatives of local public, regional and central public administrations. This event revealed that Huete was an example of innovative heritage management. Indeed, the Research Support Centre of the Madrid Complutense University will conduct the geophysical exploration work on the Alvar-Fañez hill, which evidences roman mosaic remains.

The social interaction network is made up of 375 Foundation's Friends, who economically collaborate every year voluntarily with activities that favour heritage. It is noteworthy that 71% of the Foundation's Friends do not normally live in Huete, which makes this network an innovative support mechanism. This network has helped to engage the population, including young people, to participate in the heritage recovery process. It has also raised awareness about its own importance for Huete's economic, cultural and social development.

5.2.4. Produced social changes

This point analyses the social impact, identified as positive changes in people's behaviour. This social change has been driven through institutional mechanisms and practices that promote engaging the population through collaborative participation. The interviews helped to identify these mechanisms and practices and to classify them (see

Table 3

Summary of the mechanisms of change through Positive Social Change (PSC).

Levels	Innovative management	Mechanisms of change
Motivation	Physical recovery of heritage Cultural activities The Trust's professional competence	Local population participating in heritage recovery Making voluntary payments
Capacity	Awareness campaigns about local products Architectural recovery of historic buildings Educational activities Innovative ideas competition	Generating entrepreneurship Revaluating heritage Social awareness Social engagement
Opportunity	Heritagisation Consolidating social interaction networks	Triple the number of visitors Innovation Creating jobs Engaging young people Diffusing results

Table 3) in accordance with the three PSC approach levels: Motivation, Capacity and Opportunity (Stephan et al., 2016).

In relation to the Motivation level, 56% of those interviewed stated that the Foundation's management had promoted the appearance of the "emotional value", "personal satisfaction", the "historic value" and "heritage wealth" (intrinsic motivations) felt by both the interested parties and the local population. These intrinsic motivations were what inspired voluntary activities to favour Huete's heritage enrichment. For instance, the Foundation's Friends voluntarily and periodically provide economic resources. Another example is the voluntary restoration of the pictorial heritage of Huete's parish churches. Moreover, 20% of the interviewees indicated that they felt motivated by tangible results, like the restoration works done on churches, convents, museums, socio-cultural revitalisation activities, and the economic profit made by increasing tourism and businesses, and by creating new employment sources for young people (extrinsic motivations). Another 20% did not perceive that managing heritage mechanisms favoured some form of motivation for the local population. Finally, the remaining 4% considered that the professionalism, level of knowledge and experience of FHF representatives (extrinsic motivations) were the main reasons that motivated them to show an interest in heritage and its relevance in rural terms.

At the Capacity level, 80% of those interviewed identified heritage intervention activities to be mechanisms that stimulated knowledge building and the participation of all interested parties. Of these activities, they stressed: awareness campaigns about producing and eating the Huete cucumber because they encouraged local entrepreneurship; the architectural recovery of buildings of historic interest because it favoured revaluating them by them becoming heritage and museums; the first symposium "Challenges and Opportunities of Spanish Historical Heritage in Rural Areas" as an activity that raised awareness about the importance of conserving rural heritage; the innovative ideas competition to restore heritage which encouraged the population to participate, and also annual planning. The remaining 20% did not perceive heritage recovery as a means for knowledge building or a resource to promote the local population's participation.

At the Opportunity level, Huete's architectural-cultural recovery has favoured social inclusion and building interaction networks via several mechanisms. One of them is heritagisation which has driven inland cultural tourism and has tripled the number of visitors in recent years. This circumstance has encouraged businesses to set up innovation mechanisms to better respond to tourism demand. For instance, local agro-food products were promoted at commercial sites. Both heritagisation and tourism have also promoted Huete's socio-economic development through opportunities like creating jobs and engaging the local young population. Moreover, social interaction networks have been consolidated which has favoured diffusing results locally, provincially and regionally. The interviewed technicians and responsible politicians from public administrations with rural heritage competences stressed

that each project and activity was an opportunity to improve and correct any mistakes found in the management process. They also emphasised that suitable planning, monitoring and assessing ensure sustainable projects.

6. Conclusions

Three research questions were the framework of the present study. The first question was: “**Which factors made it hard and/or easy for management to recover heritage?**” The applied participative approach revealed that Huete’s architectural-cultural heritage has been conditioned by economic and social factors as a result of its declining population in the past 60 years. Investing in recovering heritage has been limited for years by the small budget that the public administration provided for this purpose, along with previous administrations not showing any interest at all. In this context, recovering Huete’s heritage was driven when FHF was set up. Its representatives have searched for public-private subsidies to materialise activities and projects to favour heritage. Since 2008, this work has been reinforced through the emotional value that the town’s heritage wealth stirred. A limited economic budget is currently perceived as the main difficulty, but has also helped to build and consolidate support networks that have channelled the required human and economic resources. Moreover, the Foundation’s work has provided positive results in both the province and the region.

Question 2: “**What were the main drivers of impact by which the heritage management results were diffused?**” The main drivers of impact correspond to the physical recovery of places of heritage interest and the creation of cultural activities involving the local population in planning, and setting up economic, research and social networks. The Foundation has intended the results to be tangible and diffused fairly to the whole local population and to those who do not normally live in Huete via a network of friends in tune with FHF’s vision. The objective of this task is to generate a positive social, cultural and economic impact. Along these lines, architectural-cultural heritage recovery has led to tourist development; the creation of job sources; innovation projects and entrepreneurship; and to young people engaging in and being committed to the Foundation’s work. This generational renewal will help to sustain the Foundation.

Question 3: “**What main social changes have been made by highlighting heritage?**” The heritage recovery and revaluation process has had a social impact that has promoted changes in the Huete community’s behaviour. These changes in behaviour are reflected in: social participation in various projects and activities that favour heritage run by FHF; the annual increase in the Friends’ network through voluntary payments; and the generation of enterprising and innovative projects that revalue local products. This social change has taken place through several institutional mechanisms and practices that have encouraged vertical-horizontal diffusions of the results. It is necessary to keep promoting this social change by strengthening the capacities of local stakeholders and by generating knowledge related to public policy-making and resource management within the institutions and organisations that intervene in heritage recovery. To a great extent, meeting a land’s requirements depends on human, social and political capacities (Parrado et al., 2009) and must be worked on intensely to identify those local and state stakeholders with negotiation, representation, authority, social mobilisation and collective action capacities.

The actions for the recovery of the architectural heritage have also contributed to creating a new sensibility to land use policy in the local administration and the Huete population. Comprehensive interventions on architectural elements and their spaces have brought new uses that have an impact on the improvement of the quality of life of the population, the valorization of popular architecture, and the promotion of new economic activities.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A

List of the questions asked during individual interviews with representatives of the Foundation, Friends of the Foundation, representatives of different Huete associations and local people.

- **Stage 1.** The questions asked to identify factors of motivation and stimulus:

1. How did the idea about creating a Foundation in Huete come about? With whom were the first interactions made?
2. What do you think motivated the FHF being created?
3. What were the defined long-term goals? Who participated in defining these goals?
4. What was the population’s level of architectural-cultural heritage knowledge? Did the people feel identified with it or did they feel any apathy?

- **Stage 2.** The questions asked to identify interaction networks and co-creation processes:

1. What were the first ideas that engaged the Foundation? Who participated in considering these ideas?
2. What was the leadership like in the Foundation’s team?
3. Which organisations constantly supported the Foundation? How did they support it?
4. What difficulties or risks were encountered? Who were involved in solving problems?
5. How did the process to engage the population with the Foundation come about?
6. Were activities/workshops/meetings held to work together on new ideas or to improve the heritage management process?
7. Was any follow-up of the undertaken projects done?

- **Stage 3.** The questions asked to identify the mechanisms followed to diffuse and consolidate the results:

1. Do you know about any new projects/innovative activities that have emerged in the last 10 years? What are they?
2. What do you think has currently favoured the innovative environment in Huete?
3. What factors do you think have made it hard for innovation to develop?
4. What activities/projects managed by the Foundation do you think were the most important? Why?
5. What activities do you think should be maintained? Which ones should not?

- **Stage 4.** The questions asked to identify improvement to the environment and social change:

1. Have you noticed a social change in the Huete population after the Foundation has worked for 10 years?
2. Do you think that the social relations in Huete have improved? Have new interaction networks been created?
3. To what extent are you satisfied with heritage recovery?
4. What do you think must be improved to obtain better results?
5. Do you think the situation that Huete is now in would be the same if the Foundation had not been set up?

6. Do you think that the results of managing heritage recovery live up to the population's expectations?

References

- Alvarez, S., Douthwaite, B., Thiele, G., Mackay, R., Córdoba, D., Tehelen, K., 2010. Participatory impact pathways analysis: a practical method for project planning and evaluation. *Dev. Pract.* 20, 946–958. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09614524.2010.513723>.
- Amit-Cohen, I., Sofer, M., 2016. Cultural heritage and its economic potential in rural society: the case of the kibbutzim in Israel. *Land Use Policy* 57, 368–376. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.05.031>.
- Baynes, J., Herbohn, J., Dressler, W., 2016. Power relationships: their effect on the governance of community forestry in the Philippines. *Land Use Policy* 54, 169–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.01.008>.
- Bustillos Ardaya, A., Evers, M., Ribbe, L., 2019. Participatory approaches for disaster risk governance? exploring participatory mechanisms and mapping to close the communication gap between population living in flood risk areas and authorities in Nova Friburgo Municipality, RJ, Brazil. *Land Use Policy* 88, 104103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.104103>.
- Caravaca, I., Colorado, D., Fernández, V., Paneque, P., Puente, R., 1996. Patrimonio cultural y desarrollo regional. *Eure* 22, 89–99.
- Carpio, J., 2000. Desarrollo local para un nuevo desarrollo rural. *An. De. Geogr. De. la Univ. Complut.* 85–100.
- Córdoba, D., White, D., 2011. Citizen participation in managing water Do Conversatorios generate collective action? p. 66.
- Cundill, G., Thondhlana, G., Sisitka, L., Shackleton, S., Blore, M., 2013. Land claims and the pursuit of co-management on four protected areas in South Africa. *Land Use Policy* 35, 171–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2013.05.016>.
- Dela, E., Anril, S., 2019. Tourism, heritage and cultural performance: Developing a modality of heritage tourism 31, 301–309. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tmp.2019.06.001>.
- Dietz, T., 2013. Bringing values and deliberation to science communication. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 110, 14081–14087. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1212740110>.
- Douthwaite, B., Alvarez, S., Cook, S., Davies, R., George, P., Howell, J., Mackay, R., Rubiano, J., 2007. Participatory impact pathways analysis: a practical application of program theory in research for development. *Can. J. Program Eval.* 22, 127–159.
- Douthwaite, B., Alvarez, S., Thiele, G., Mackay, R., 2008. Participatory impact pathways analysis: A practical method for project planning and evaluation. *Institutional Learning and Change ILAC* 1–4.
- Eker, S., Daalen, E., van, Thissen, W., 2017. Incorporating stakeholder perspectives into model-based scenarios: exploring the futures of the Dutch gas sector. *Futures* 93, 27–43. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2017.08.002>.
- Erfani, G., Roe, M., 2019. Institutional stakeholder participation in urban redevelopment in Tehran: an evaluation of decisions and actions. *Land Use Policy*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2019.104367>.
- Ericson, J.A., 2006. A participatory approach to conservation in the Calakmul Biosphere Reserve, Campeche, Mexico. *Landscape Urban Plan.* 74, 242–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2004.09.006>.
- Fatorić, S., Seekamp, E., 2017. Evaluating a decision analytic approach to climate change adaptation of cultural resources along the Atlantic Coast of the United States. *Land Use Policy* 68, 254–263. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2017.07.052>.
- Florido Trujillo, G., 2013. El patrimonio territorial en el plan de ordenación del territorio de Andalucía: indefiniciones y dificultades para un conocimiento preciso. *Bol. De. la Asoc. De. Geógrafos Esp.* 63, 173–202. <https://doi.org/10.21138/bage.1611>.
- Fundación Huete Futuro, 2009–2019. Boletines del nº 1 al nº 25 (no press).
- Fung, A., 2006. Varieties of participation in complex governance. *Public Adm. Rev.* 66, 66–75. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-6210.2006.00667.x>.
- Gera, W., 2016. Public participation in environmental governance in the Philippines: the challenge of consolidation in engaging the state. *Land Use Policy* 52, 501–510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2014.02.021>.
- González, L., 2016. Huete. Nuevas Oportunidades desde las Humanidades. Cuenca, España: Asociación de Amigos del Museo Etnográfico de Huete.
- Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2020. Cifras oficiales de población resultantes de la revisión del padrón municipal a 1 de enero. (<https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=2869>) (Accessed 29 July 2020).
- Jimura, T., 2011. The impact of world heritage site designation on local communities - a case study of Oigimachi, Shirakawa-mura, Japan. *Tour. Manag.* 32, 288–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2010.02.005>.
- Junta de Andalucía. Consejería de Vivienda y Ordenación del Territorio, 2006. Plan de Ordenación del Territorio de Andalucía (POTA).
- Knowlton, L.W., Phillips, C.C., 2012. *The Logic Model Guidebook. Better Strategies for Great Results*, Second ed. SAGE Publications Ltd.,
- Koutsouris, A., Zarokosta, E., 2019. Supporting bottom-up innovative initiatives throughout the spiral of innovations: lessons from rural Greece. *J. Rural Stud.* 73, 176–185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2019.10.046>.
- Kovács, E., Fabók, V., Kálóczkai, Á., Hansen, H.P., 2016. Towards understanding and resolving the conflict related to the Eastern Imperial Eagle (Aquila heliaca) conservation with participatory management planning. *Land Use Policy* 54, 158–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.02.011>.
- Kratzer, A., Ammering, U., 2019. Rural innovations in biosphere reserves – a social network approach. *J. Rural Stud.* 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2019.01.001>.
- Li, J., Krishnamurthy, S., Pereira, A., Wesemael, P. Van, 2020. Community participation in cultural heritage management: a systematic literature review comparing Chinese and international practices. *Cities* 96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2019.102476>.
- Li, Y., Westlund, H., Liu, Y., 2019. Why some rural areas decline while some others not: an overview of rural evolution in the world. *J. Rural Stud.* 68, 135–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2019.03.003>.
- Lista Roja del Patrimonio, 2020. La Lista Roja del Patrimonio es una iniciativa de la Asociación Hispania Nostra. Madrid, España. (<https://listarojapatrimonio.org/>) (Accessed 20 April 2020).
- López, A., Rincón, W., Hidalgo, M. del C., Domingo, M., 2012. El Catálogo Monumental de España (1900–1961). Ministerio de Cultura de España.
- Markey, S., Halsey, G., Manson, D., 2008. Challenging the inevitability of rural decline: advancing the policy of place in northern British Columbia. *J. Rural Stud.* 24, 409–421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2008.03.012>.
- Martín, I., Martín, F., 2016. Interpretación del patrimonio y gestión sostenible del turismo en espacios rurales. Los casos de montejo de la sierra y patones. *Boletín de la Asociación de Geógrafos Españoles* 72, 169–193. <https://doi.org/10.21138/bage.e.2336>.
- Mayne, J., 2004. Reporting on outcomes: setting performance expectations and telling performance stories. *Can. J. Program Eval.* 19, 31–60.
- Medina, F.X., 2017. Reflexiones sobre el patrimonio y la alimentación desde las perspectivas cultural y turística. *An. De. Antropol.* 51, 106–113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.antro.2017.02.001>.
- Moulin, C., Boniface, P., 2010. Routeing heritage for tourism: making heritage and cultural tourism networks for socio-economic development. *Int. J. Herit. Stud.* 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13527250120079411>.
- Parrado, A., Aranda, Y., Gutiérrez, O., Molina, J.P., Pachón, F., Parra, C., Parra, J.E., Angel, J., Villarraga, V., 2009. Núcleos de emprendedores rurales. Una propuesta para el desarrollo rural con enfoque territorial. ECOE.
- Pérez, E., Maya, D.L., Farah, M.A., 2002. Metodologías participativas en la formulación y planificación del proyecto de desarrollo rural. Cuadernos de Desarrollo rural.
- Prats, L., 2005. Concepto y gestión del patrimonio local. *Cuad. De. Antropol. Soc.* 21, 17–35. <https://doi.org/http://www.redalyc.org/articulo.oa?id=180913910002>.
- Provenzano, V., Arnone, M., Seminara, M.S., 2016. Innovation in the rural areas and the linkage with the Quintuple Helix Model. *Procedia Soc. Behav. Sci.* 223, 442–447. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2016.05.269>.
- Richards, M., Panfil, S., 2010. Manual para la evaluación del impacto social de los proyectos de carbono terrestre. Parte II-Caja de herramientas de métodos y materiales de apoyo.
- Rodríguez, I., 1998. Nuevas perspectivas en la protección del patrimonio arqueológico en el medio rural. *Complutum* 9, 293–310.
- Servicio Público de Empleo Estatal SEPE, 2018. Informe del Mercado de Trabajo de Cuenca. Datos del 2017. Madrid, España (Accessed 10 May 2020).
- Stenseke, M., 2009. Land Use Policy Local participation in cultural landscape maintenance: Lessons from Sweden 26, 214–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2008.01.005>.
- Stephan, U., Patterson, M., Kelly, C., Mair, J., 2016. Organizations driving positive social change: a review and an integrative framework of change processes. *J. Manag.* 42, 1250–1281. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206316633268>.
- Toderi, M., Francioni, M., Seddaiu, G., Roggero, P.P., Trozzo, L., D'Ottavio, P., 2017. Bottom-up design process of agri-environmental measures at a landscape scale: evidence from case studies on biodiversity conservation and water protection. *Land Use Policy* 68, 295–305. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2017.08.002>.
- Troitiño, M.Á., 1998. Patrimonio arquitectónico, cultural y territorio. *Ciudades: Revista del Instituto Universitario de Urbanística de la Universidad de Valladolid* 95–104. <https://doi.org/10.24197/ciudades.04.1998.95-104>.